

D1.1

Part 2

Map and Gap Analysis

Consortium:

Bay Zoltán
Nonprofit Ltd.
for Applied Research

EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION
OF APPLIED DESIGNERS

MOHOLY-NAGY
MŰVÉSZETI EGYETEM
UNIVERSITY OF ART AND
DESIGN BUDAPEST

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 www.engage4bio.eu

 info@engage4bio.eu

@Engage4BIO

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Part 2

Manual and Canvases

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AUTHORS

Harriëtte Bos, Remco
Kranendonk, Alwin Gerritsen,
Maarten Kootstra, Jeroen van
den Eijnde, Tjeerd Veenstra,
Viola Pinzi

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Contributors

NAME	ORGANISATION
Harriëtte Bos Remco Kranendonk Alwin Gerritsen Maarten Kootstra	WR
Jeroen van den Eijnde Tjeerd Veenstra	ArtEZ
Viola Pinzi	EAEA

Peer Reviews

NAME	ORGANISATION
Aila Maijanen	CLIC Innovation Ltd, 24.3.2023

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Partners short names

ZSI	Zentrum Fur Soziale Innovation Gmbh
WR	Stichting Wageningen Research
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
BZN	Bay Zoltan Alkalmazott Kutatasi Kozhasznu Nonprofit Kft.
EAEA	European Association For The Education Of Adults
MOME	Moholy-Nagy Muveszeti Egyetem
artEZ	Stichting Artez
CLIC	Clic Innovation Oy
TMG	Business Upper Austria – Oo Irtschaftsagentur Gmbh
MET	Metropolia Ammattikorkeakoulu Oy
UNIPA	Università Degli Studi Di Palermo

Abbreviations

COR	Committee of the Regions
EGD	European Green Deal
NGO	Non Governmental Organization
RIS3	Regional Innovation Strategies Smart Specializations
SME	Small and Medium Sized Enterprise
TRL	Technological Readiness Level

1 Introduction: Part 2 - Collaborative map analysis

1.1 Methodology

The Map & Gap analyses Identify and analyze the potential for regional bioeconomy developments and the knowledge and innovation gaps, by developing formats for the regional Hubs and will support the hubs to understand different concepts and the needed actors for the transition to the bioeconomy. By this mapping process, hubs will identify what they currently have, the level of involvement and maturity of what they currently have, but also what they need in the nearby future. The map will be a framework to think and act for future development scenarios towards a regional bioeconomy.

- Method: interviews or workshop/s (based on the canvas),
- In case of workshop: Engage4Bio Hub coordinator, Engage4Bio research partner, small group of local partners (public, private, knowledge, society, intermediate), who are able to describe the current situation from the different perspectives.
- In case of workshop: prepare well the exercises to fill in the 4 canvas templates. Form different groups of people who are able to contribute to multiple canvases. The exercise can also be organized with Miro-board, to collect input for the canvas.
- In case of workshop, a moderator is needed, preferably an Engage4Bio partner.
- Based on the inputs from interviews of the results of a workshop, a report of the mapping of the current situation should be made (based on report template)

1.2 Canvas Bioeconomy

<p>Actors</p> <p>How many and which companies are involved?</p> <p>Are these SMEs/large companies/mixed? What is the share between large companies/SMEs?</p> <p>What different sectors are involved?</p> <p>Who are the Value Chain partners?</p> <p>How are the companies organised? Do the companies have other industry platforms / associations / federations representing and influencing their joint goals?</p>	<p>Technology and activities</p> <p>What kind of technologies are applied in your hub?</p> <p>What is the TRL level of the activities in your hub?</p>	<p>Value proposition and products</p> <p>What kind of (consumer) products are produced in your hub?</p> <p>Where would you position your hub in the bioeconomy graph?</p> <p>Do you have circular activities in your hub?</p>	<p>Customers and citizens</p> <p>What kind of customers does your hub produce for? (businesses or consumers?)</p> <p>Are these customers locally/nationally/internationally located?</p> <p>What kind of citizens are involved in your hub activities?</p>	<p>External influences</p> <p>What kind of external influences will impact your near and more distant future? (EU policy, EPR, market forces, etc)</p>
	<p>Resources and feedstock</p> <p>What are the main (material) resources for the production in your hub?</p> <p>Are they sourced locally/nationally/internationally ?</p> <p>Are they new or recycled or otherwise?</p> <p>What kind of side streams do you have and how do you handle them?</p> <p>How do circular activities provide value and to whom, in your hub?</p>		<p>Channels</p> <p>Are your hub activities in general visible to citizens?</p> <p>Does your hub advertise locally? How do companies sell the products?</p>	

Threats

What are the main threats you see in the (further) transition towards a circular bioeconomy?

What are the main threats that could impact the viability of your hub?

Opportunities

How do you see your hub in 15 years' time (what are your ambitions in terms of circularity, bioeconomy, growth or expansion, size)?

What opportunities do you identify in terms of increasing sustainability or circularity and bioeconomy activities in your hub?

How are opportunities identified in your hub and how are development activities organized?

Do you have connections with R&D parties, education parties, or others, to develop the opportunities you see?

1.3 Canvas regional development

<p>Playing field</p> <p>Who are the key actors in advancing the bioeconomy in your hub?</p> <p>What actor domains are present? Public, private, knowledge, education, society</p> <p>Who are missing?</p> <p>What are the formal competences of involved partners?</p> <p>How is action between different actors coordinated? Is there a network or cluster organisation?</p>	<p>Capacities</p> <p>What capacities are available for developing the regional bioeconomy, in terms of human capital, knowledge and skills..</p> <p>Is there an established ongoing dialogue and cooperation between sectors, between public and private sectors, involving NGOs and representatives of the civil society?</p>	<p>Mission</p> <p>What is the current state of the bioeconomy in your hub?</p> <p>What are its impacts on the region?</p> <p>What objectives for the bioeconomy do regional actors share and what are the differences?</p> <p>Is there a regional bioeconomy strategy and what does it aim for?</p> <p>Is there a clear mission? [tactical strategy]</p>	<p>Specialisation</p> <p>What are the regional strengths, opportunities and comparative advantages for your bioeconomy hub and region?</p> <p>What strategic choices have been made regarding a specialization within the bioeconomy?</p>	<p>Innovation pipeline</p> <p>What activities are initiated to foster the bioeconomy in your hub?</p> <p>How mature is the regional bioeconomy in its development?</p> <p>What facilities and/or other supporting infrastructure are present?</p> <p>How well is the bioeconomy hub anchored in civil society and within the strategies and activities of other quadruple helix actors? Please, mention 3 or more examples.</p>
	<p>Finance</p> <p>How are these activities financed?</p> <p>Is funding available for initiatives and investments in the bioeconomy?</p>		<p>Learning</p> <p>Is there a network of regional actors for joint learning -how is this organised? Does this learning process lead to adjusted and new activities? What are strong and weak points?</p>	

Existing conditions – challenges and obstacles	Requirements – opportunities and enablers
<p>What are the current challenges and obstacles for bioeconomy activities described above?</p> <p><i>Please list at least 3 challenges/obstacles providing some contextualization. Please provide relevant example at different level, such as policy, strategic planning, funding, participation, community support, etc.</i></p>	<p>What are the main enabling factors of the current bioeconomy hub, its mission and supporting activities?</p> <p>What opportunities there are to develop further the bioeconomy hub, its mission and supporting activities?</p> <p>What outputs and outcomes are needed for the short term?</p>

1.4 Canvas Arts and Design

<p>Key Partners</p> <p>Who are already involved in the mentioned Key activities or providing Key resources? Individuals, companies, organisations, or other entities?</p>	<p>Key Activities</p> <p>Which key activities are already running in your hub to support your intended role for art & design?</p>	<p>Role of Art & Design</p> <p>Choose here one of the 4 described roles for art & design approaches. Relate all the other building blocks of the canvas to the chosen role.</p>	<p>Partner Relationships</p> <p>What type of relationship do you have with your mentioned key partners and citizens & learners?</p>	<p>Citizens & Learners</p> <p>Which citizens and (non-) formal learners are you already addressing by your key art & design activities?</p>
	<p>Key Resources</p> <p>Which key resources (finance & facilities) do already support the mentioned key activities</p>		<p>Channels</p> <p>Which means do you have to communicate, continue, and strengthen the relationships with your mentioned key partners and citizens & learners?</p>	
<p>Weaknesses & Threats</p> <p>Describe the weakness and treads of the existing key partners, activities, resources, partner relationships, channels and addressed citizens and learners. Think about the level and maturity of involvement, interest, impact, etc.</p>		<p>Strength & Opportunities</p> <p>Describe the strength and opportunities of the existing key partners, activities and resources, partner relationships, channels and addressed citizens and learners.</p>		

Questions to explain and inspire input for canvas 1 Arts and Design

Key activities:

- Do you have any activities to showcase best practices for art & design in the context of the bioeconomy (exhibitions, presentations, design weeks, business events, regional festivals, art events, etc.)?
- Do you have any activities in the field of research, innovation, policy making etc. In which artists and designers are involved to create a common space for understanding and knowledge sharing (brainstorm, pressure cooker and co-creation sessions, research and innovation projects, events for citizens participation, educational and public presentations, etc.)?
- Do you have any initiatives or activities in which artists and designers are asked to create events or campaigns to create awareness for citizens and learners (poster and social media campaigns, arts and design events, etc.)?
- Do you have any activities which support and strengthen skills and experience of artists and designers for playing their intended role in the best way?

Key partners:

- Do you have educational institutes which have the needed art & design expertise (art school, creative departments of universities, universities of applied sciences, vocational schools, etc.)?
- Do you have creative agencies, studios and professional artists and designers in your hub which have the expertise for the described roles?
- Do you have creative network organizations, platforms or interest groups within the creative industry which can support the described role for art & design?
- Do you have public or private funders for individuals, profit and non-profit organizations in the field of the creative industry to support the described roles?
- Do you have institutes and organizations which can showcase best practices from art & design (museums, galleries, cultural foundations, foundations for innovation, etc.)?

Key Resources

- Do have spatial facilities and equipment to showcase best practices, to do research and innovation projects (public and private labs, community spaces, studios for artists and designers, makerspaces, etc.)
- Do you have public or private funders for research and innovation which are open for creative professionals?

Partner relationships

- What kind of relationships do you have with your key partners (formal/non-formal, professional/private, institutional/network, etc.)?

Channels

- What are the communication tools with your key partners, citizens learners (off-line/online communication tools, network events, regular formal/non-formal meetings, etc.)

Citizens & Learners

- Are there specific groups of citizens & learners who you would like to address for the transition to the bioeconomy (for instance related to age, gender, social-economic and/or cultural background, specific groups within the quadruple helix, etc.)

1.5 Canvas Lifelong learning for Bioeconomy

<p>Actors</p> <p>Who are the key actors currently providing educational and training programmes of relevance for the purpose of bioeconomy practice uptake in the area/region?</p> <p>What different sectors are involved?</p> <p>What different kind of education providers are involved?</p>	<p>Technology and activities</p> <p>What kind of learning activities and programmes are offered?</p> <p><i>Please, provide an overview in terms of type (formal, non-formal, awareness raising etc.), level (secondary school, higher education etc.) and formats (online, face to face, duration etc.), for various topics (skills) that are relevant for bioeconomy.</i></p> <p><i>Please mention also the learning methods, if known, and what kind of innovation level they have.</i></p>	<p>Value proposition and activities</p> <p>What is the impact of the current educational offer for the various learners groups?</p> <p>What is the impact for the bioeconomy practices uptake?</p>	<p>Audience/learners</p> <p>Who are the main audiences/learners of the learning activities?</p> <p><i>Please, provide an overviews and link to the type of learning activities mapped.</i></p>	<p>External influences</p> <p>Which kind of enablers or challenges not directly related to the regional context or sector have an impact on the current educational provisions?</p> <p><i>Please, list a few enablers and a few challenges/obstacles.</i></p>
	<p>Resources</p> <p>How these mapped learning activities are funded and supported?</p>		<p>Channels</p> <p>How are the relevant learning activities you have described promoted to relevant</p>	

	<p><i>Please, provide an overview of the sources of funding, other forms of support and the impact on the activities relevance for the current bioeconomics practices.</i></p>		<p>potential learners? Which channels are used and how efficient and impactful are they?</p>	
<p>Challenges and obstacles</p> <p>What are the current challenges and obstacles for the provision of the education and learning activities described above?</p> <p><i>Please list at least 3 challenges/obstacles providing some contextualization.</i></p> <p><i>Please provide relevant example at different level, such as policy, strategic planning, funding, participation, community support, etc, including also reference to the core dimensions of regional development for bioeconomic.</i></p>		<p>Opportunities and enablers</p> <p>What are the main enabling factors of the current educational provision of educational activities linked/relevant to bioeconomics?</p> <p>What are the opportunities to develop further the current for the provision of the education and learning activities described above?</p> <p><i>Please list at least 3 enablers and 3 opportunities and provide some context.</i></p> <p><i>Please provide relevant example at different level, such as policy, strategic planning, funding, participation, community support, etc, including also reference to the core dimensions of regional development for bioeconomic.</i></p>		

1.6 Learning activities scenarios

To complete the gap analysis exercise around learning activities, we would kindly ask you to provide also a short concepts for 3 learning scenarios for the implementation of potential new learning activities addressing the needs identified above and that the Hub assesses could have a positive impact in terms of the challenges.

Scenario	Title	Description	Actors	Learning purpose	Learners
1					
2					
3					

1.7 Report template

Once the analysis above are concluded and validated with the participants, we kindly ask each Hub coordinator to prepare a written report using the template here below (to be delivered together with the filled in canvas for Practice 1 and 2 and the Scenario table). We would expect a report of about 6-10 pages in total, providing the highlights of the analysis from the canvas and more detailed/in-depth information on the aspects mentioned there, in particular related to challenges, obstacles, opportunities and enablers.

Executive summary

- Key highlights from mapping and gap analysis results (1 page)

Introduction

- Explanation of the methods and processes for the analysis (Please, describe all the activities carried out for the mapping and gap analysis, with time, methods, tools etc.)
- Description of participants and their role in the process (*Please, describe the participants, how the groups were organised, contacted and selected, their general level of engagement and participation. Please, also add the full list of participants in Annex 1*)
- Feedback on the analysis and process from the hubs coordinator/organiser and from the participants (*Please, ensure to collect feedback on the process from participants, in each activity you organise*).

Mapping

- Description of identified activities, initiatives etc., including actors and their role and engagement
- Resources (funding/support/capacity) for current activities
- Challenges and obstacles
- Enablers and opportunities
- Lesson learnt and conclusions

Gap analysis

- Description of identified needs, including actors and their role and engagement
- Potential resources (funding/support/capacity) to develop new/enhanced activities

- Value proposition and expected impact of new/proposed activities
- Challenges and obstacles
- Enablers and opportunities
- Needs analysis conclusions

Learning activities scenarios

- Description of the proposed learning activities
- Rationale and links with needs (*Please, provide details on the rationale and how these activities would respond to the needs analysis*)

Conclusions and next steps

- Main overall conclusions from the analysis
- Key guidelines and recommendations for the coming activities of the hub

Annex 1 – List of participants (name, organisation, role)

Annex 2 – Canvas filled 1 (at least one for each perspective for each phase)

“ Multi-stakeholder engagement to strengthen regional bioeconomy value-chains ”

Consortium :

 www.engage4bio.eu

 info@engage4bio.eu

@Engage4BIO

